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STUDY OF DRUG RELATED PROBLEMS IN ORGAN TRANSPLANT PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Early graft rejection was the issue, due to current use of drugs like immunosuppressant, transplantation is successful and rarely rejection of graft is been seen. It is quite common for the occurrence of drug related problems in Organ transplant patients, hence they need extra care to identify and resolve these. Multiple co-morbidities conditions and drugs can be a reason for DRP. With an increase in the comorbid conditions resulting in an increase number of prescribed drugs for its treatment. Total of 224 Drug Related Problems (DRP) are found in study population which Drug interaction is commonly identified were like Drug interactions (n=214, 95.11%) adverse drug reactions (n=10, 4.44%). With the introduction of services by clinical pharmacist which can help resolving various DRP hence optimising patient care. Reliable data from the population have helped in implementing drug safety programmes were the main focus was on co-prescription errors in the population. It is difficult to manage existing technology without having idea about problem which can occur. Complete discussion is beyond the scope of the current study that physician often ignore potential drug problems.

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INTRODUCTION

Organ transplantation is the optimal therapy given these days to the end stage organ failure patients. Reports say that 85% of graft survival cases are found with transplantation of organ like kidney, liver and heart. Due to current use of drugs like immunosuppressant, transplantation is successful and rarely rejection of graft is been seen (1-2). Different Immunosuppressants act on different phases for mechanism of the same. The evolution started when murray and his co-workers performed first kidney transplantation between monozygotic twins, where there was no immunosuppressants (3-4). Early graft rejection was the issue, where even the total body irradiation was done prior to the transplantation in America and France to ablate recipient immune system to overcome rejection but the variable results were fatal (5-6). Advances in the transplantation existed when 6-mercaptopurine was found to have immunological reaction against foreign protein in rabbits which later helped in prolong survival of grafts (7-8). Immunosuppressive agents include like calcineurin inhibitors, anti-metabolites, mTOR inhibitors, steroids and antibody based therapies. These agents can act on different sites in the T cell activation cascade, mainly by inhibiting T cell activation or proliferation. Selection of the agents is based upon the type of medical history and physician opinion. Different agents act on the different pathway of T cell response, where dose adjustment can help reduce side effects. Currently Calcineurin inhibitors are greatly used in transplantations about 95%. There is well known risk of these drugs on prolonged use like renal impairment (9) metabolic changes, neurotoxicity and de novo malignancies (10).

Though many immunosuppressive agents are used these days, rejection of human homografts is observed. This can be studied in depth with transplantations in dogs, rats, pigs and humans when sequences of events occur when modified or unmodified recipients reject the graft (11). Accumulation of immunosuppressants in the blood vessels has increased possibility that the damage can later lead to late rejection of the organ due to circulating antibody. Deposition of the drugs is less in liver when compared to kidney transplants (12) where the hepatic graft rejection is called as cell mediated immunity as it is opposed by circulating antibodies. As Rejection defined by (13) and also Williams and Calne (14), where patients treated with conventional immunosuppressants also occurs with cyclosporine A and steroids. Degree of rejection varies at unpredictable times and at different combinations. Resulting patterns are categorized as anicteric, indolent and crisis (13). Acute cellular rejection is encountered by doing biopsy after many years of transplantation. Some patients are advised to discontinue medications and other patients would have been advised unwise to lower the maintenance medications. Substitute of steroid therapy was given at this point. Re-transplantation is the only treatment for survival given to the patients whose first grafts were rejected either early or late. Morbidity arising due to chronic use of immunosuppressants is an incentive to know the lowest level of drugs which is important to maintain stable graft function. Complete freedom from immunosuppressants can be possible for only long term surviving recipients of liver (15), kidney (16) initiated prospective trial of drug weaning (17). It was shown that significant reduction in medications would be safely accomplished. Guidelines for judicious use should be clarified and danger consequences of graft rejection are to be known.

Every surface of the cell has a marker which is slightly different in different individuals. The codes for the gene are found linked to the 6-chromosome in humans. These are called as HLA (Human Leukocyte Antigen) and are determined by 5 different linked genes. They are polymorphic in nature. Twins usually have same HLA alleles and so same antigens when it comes to transplantation. A graft can be transplanted successfully from one part of host to the other part. But when it is done in two different individuals, it rejects and it sloughs off in the recipient body. It is when done in identical twins it would be compatible & successful due to similar HLA alleles and antigens. Transplantation of tissue from one area to another in same person is said to be as autograft. Due to multiple alleles of HLA gene it became difficult to match with strangers. If a graft from a donor is transplanted to unrelated recipient, the antigen HLA are found to be different results in rejection. Immune system of host graft will lead as foreign object leading to graft rejection. Graft made from same species but different genetics are said as homografts (18).

It is in the very nature of drugs that they will cause adverse reactions. However, the incidence rates of specific adverse drug reactions vary considerably from drug to drug. In the same way, certain high-risk groups of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) with specific drugs will always exist. The World Health Organization (WHO) database is the largest international database of case reports of spontaneous reporting of suspected ADRs. The current procedure of signal generation is as follows: On a quarterly basis, lists of potential drug ADR problems are generated on new reports received at the centre. One important subset is medication errors, in part, because they are relatively common, and, in part, because they increase the risk for adverse drug events. The latter is thought to be responsible for nearly 7,000 lives lost and up to an estimated \$136 billion spent annually in additional health care costs (19)(20)(21)(22).

Clinical risk management aims to change the organisation from its vulnerability to integrity. It can be categorised into three phases: assessment, management and evaluation of strategies. In assessment the hazards are identified and stratified with clinical significance, where management leads to minimising the same (23). Limited number of studies is performed related to the magnitude of drug interactions in the community pharmacy sector (24). We are interested in conducting study which relate to such problem occurring in real daily practices, focusing on general practices, patient specific and hazardous drug interactions (25). Along with the prevalence and nature of drug-drug interaction alerts (identification of risk), we were interested in the analysis and management phase in the risk management process. Therefore, the main aim for this study was to obtain frequency, nature and management of drug related problems.

Table No: 1.

Types of transplantation:
Allogenic
Autograft
Isograft
Xenograft and xenotransplantation
Split transplants
Domino transplants
ABO-incompatible transplants

Table No: 2.

Class of immunosuppressant agents and drugs:	
Corticosteroid	Prednisolone Prednisone Methyl prednisolone
Anti-proliferative	Azathioprine Mycophenolatemofetil Mycophenolate sodium
Calcineurin inhibitor	Cyclosporine Tacrolimus
TOR inhibitor	Sirolimus Everolimus
Polyclonal anti-lymphocyte antibodies	ALG ATG ALS
Monoclonal antibodies	Muromonab-CD3 BasiliximabDaclizumab

OBJECTIVES

- To identify and detect drug related problems in Organ Transplant patients.
- To categorize and management of the drug related problems.

METHODOLOGY

This was a prospective, observational and non-interventional study. It was carried out for 6 month of duration in a quaternary care hospital. Study mainly involves the enrolment of patient who had undergone transplantation of kidney, liver and heart. This study was approved by Institutional Ethical Committee of PES College of Pharmacy, Bengaluru. The required collection of data was done and prior to which informed consent form was taken from participants. Data collection form was made with respect to the information needed for the study and by referring available literatures. It includes patient demographics, monthly laboratory results, patient medication chart and the two categories of drug related problems such as drug interactions and adverse drug reactions. Inclusion criteria mainly were the inclusion of all the age groups of Organ Transplant patient taking medications of both gender patients are included in the study. Exclusion criteria were pregnant women and Patients who were not willing to participate and consent in the study were excluded.

Study procedure started with Informed consent form which was given to the patients who were willing to participate in the study. Medication related patients were identified through review of the patient chart, electronic medical record, patient interview and communication with other healthcare disciplines. All MRP are categorized by type and medication class. MRP appearance rate is determined as the number of MRP identified per month/number of months in study. The data collection form was prepared by referring patient dialysis file and drug file. The main aim of the study is to identify and report the drug related problems in critical areas of care like Organ Transplant Unit. Before collecting the necessary data, the purpose of the study was explained to the patients and informed consent form was given to the patients, who are interested to participate in the study. The data was collected from the patients was documented, for further analysis it was entered to Microsoft excel sheet.

Result analysis was done on concurrent medications, their necessity, ADR's, possible interactions, risk factors and other drug related problems were documented. The collected data was analyzed and categorized into respective drug related problems. Several suitable literatures, online resources and textbooks were reviewed to analyze the result. Correlation between DRPs and multiple medication regimens was observed.

RESULTS

A prospective observational study was conducted for over 6 months in a quaternary care hospital in which 34 organ transplant patients were enrolled, 19 liver transplant patients (16 male, 3 female) and 15 kidney transplant patients (11 male, 4 female) as given below in figure:1 & figure:2.

Figure:1– DISTRIBUTION OF ORGAN TRANSPLANT PATIENTS.

Figure:2–GENDER DISTRIBUTION IN LIVER AND KIDNEY TRANSPLANT PATIENTS.

TYPES OF INTERACTION

Total of 224 Drug Related Problems are found in study population which Drug interaction is commonly identified (n=214) 94.11%, in which 8 are clinically shown. Liver transplant patients constitute of total 85 interactions in which 4 major/use alternate (5%), 65 moderate/significant (76%), 16 minor/mild (19%) and kidney transplant patients constitute of total 129 interactions in which 13 major/use alternate (10%), 93 moderate/significant (72%), 23 minor/mild (18%) as shown in figure:3 and figure:4

FIGURE:3- DRUG INTERACTION IN LIVER PATIENTS.

FIGURE: 4- DRUG INTERACTION IN KIDNEY PATIENTS.

ADVERS DRUG REACTIONS

Most of the interaction found was immunosuppressive drugs with other drugs seen in both liver and kidney transplant patients, major drug interaction observed are

- Tacrolimus+Metoclopramide: Metoclopramide may increase tacrolimus levels, resulting in tacrolimus toxicity and acute renal failure.
- Tacrolimus+Mycophenolic acid: Tacrolimus may increase mycophenolic acid levels.
- Tacrolimus+Fluconazole: Tacrolimus is given orally, its serum levels are considerably increased by oral fluconazole.
- Furosemide+Tobramycin: Furosemide with tobramycin significantly increased the risk of nephrotoxicity and ototoxicity.
- Fluconazole+Fentanyl: Patients may experience prolonged and increased Alfentanil effects if they are given fluconazole.

We also found ADRs in over 10 cases (4.44%) in which patient mostly suffering from insomnia and itching.

TABLE:3- ADVERSE DRUG INTERACTIONS.

Sl no.	Name of the drugs	ADRs observed
1	Tacrolimus	Hypertention, Skin rash, Pruritus, Abdominal pain
2	Mycophenolic acid	Headache, Insomnia
3	Furosemide	Dizziness, Drug rash, Urticaria
4	Fluconazole	Nausea, Rash, Headache
5	Sepran DS	Hyperkalemia
6	Paracetamol	Skin rash
7	Tramadol	Constipation

Prescription of 563 drugs in various combination were prescribed for 34 patients, 19 liver transplant patients in which 16 male and 3 female patients in prescription of 298 drugs were prescribed with a mean of 15.7 ± 5.72 and 15 kidney transplant patients in which 11 males and 04 female patients in a prescription of 265 drugs were prescribed with a mean of 17.6 ± 2.86 as drugs per patients.

TABLE:4- TYPES OF PRESCRIPTION DRUGS.

Medications	Percentage (n=563)
Immunosuppressive drugs	9.6%
Anti Infective	18.3%
Steroids	9%
Anti Diabetics	4%
Anti Hypertensive	3.4%
Pain management	12.25%
Anti Emetics	5.5%
Gastric drugs	4.61%
Laxatives	5.32%
Supplements	8.34%
Anti Platelets	3%
Others	16.69%

FIGURE:5-UTILIZATION OF IMMUNOSUPPRESSANTS IN STUDYPOPULATION.

FIGURE: 6- UTILIZATION OF ANTIBIOTICS IN STUDY POPULATION.

FIGURE:7- CONTRIBUTION OF COMORBID CONDITION IN LIVER TRANSPLANT PATIENTS.

Hypertension are commonly seen in kidney transplant patients out of 15 patients, 14 (93.33%) are hypertensive under oral antihypertensive drugs like Metoprolol(6), Clonidine(1), Amlodepine(2), Terlipressin(3), Cilnidepine(2)

TRANSPLANT PATIENTS

FIGURE:-8 CONTRIBUTION OF COMORBID CONDITION IN KIDNEY.

Nutritional supplements were seen mostly in liver transplant patients than in kidney patients. Maximum patients were prescribed with zinc+folicacid(zevit) and calcium (calcimax).

FIGURE:9- MISCELLANEOUS DRUG UTILIZATION IN TRANSPLANT PATIENTS.

Pain management are used to reduce the pain in organ transplant patients, paracetamol is used mostly to reduce the pain and the temperature, the drugs prescribed in other cases are fentanyl, morphine, aspirin, buscopan are used

FIGURE:10- MISCELLANEOUS UTILIZATION OF PAIN MANAGEMENT IN TRANSPLANT PATIENTS.

Miscellaneous drugs like cetirizine, chlorthalidone, alprazolam, uditiv. asthalin, budesonide, duolin, pectolol, citralka, albumin, ambrolite, codeine phosphate are used. The number of MRP per patient drug exposures are determined using: $\{(number\ of\ patients) * (mean\ number\ of\ medications) / number\ of\ months\ of\ study\} / number\ of\ MRP\ identified$ which was 0.14 in liver patients and 0.07 in kidney patients.

DISCUSSION

It is quite common for the occurrence of drug related problems in Organ transplant patients, hence they need extra care to identify and resolve these. Multiple co-morbidities conditions and drugs can be a reason for DRP. many Published studies have reported potential Drug interactions nearly from 2.2% to 30% in hospitalized cases and from 9.2% to 70.3% in ambulatory patients. (26).

In our study, 85% patients who were undergoing immunosuppressant therapy were under tacrolimus, 74% were under mycophenolic acid, 80% of the patients were under antibiotics sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim, 53% were under piperacillin and tazobactam, 44% were under fluoroquinolones. These were the widely prescribed ones. Under the category pain management 93% of patients were under paracetamol, fentanyl was given to 24% of the patients and tramadol was given to 21%. Under the category of supplements folic acid, calcium carbonate + vitamin D3 were given. Total drugs prescribed were 592 for 34 patients. 265 drugs were prescribed to patients with kidney related treatment. The kidney transplant patient with a mean of 17.6 ± 2.86 . 298 drugs were prescribed in liver transplant patient with a mean of 15.7 ± 5.72 drugs per patients. The most common DRP that we had come across was drug interactions 224 (95.11%). A study was conducted by Juno J Joel et.al were it was concluded that Drug Interactions as the major DRP (27). Also Grabe DW et al and his co-workers in another study identified the same results in patients undergoing Organ transplantation (28)

There is always direct relationship of number of drugs prescribed and DRP. With an increase in the comorbid conditions resulting in the increase number of prescribed drugs for its treatment. Though the results are promising there is limitation for the study which includes inadequate drug details, non-updated patient details and other information, difficulty in distinguishing adverse reactions and others. In organ transplantation DRP are commonly observed. Drug Related Problems were mainly found to be of two types in our study: ADR and DDI (Drug Drug interaction) (29).

With the introduction of services by clinical pharmacist which can help resolving various DRP hence optimising patient care. Reliable data from the population have helped in implementing drug safety programmes were the main focus was on coprescription errors in the population. It is difficult to manage existing technology without having idea about problem which can occur. Complete discussion is beyond the scope of the current study that physician often ignore potential drug problems. Therefore, by clinical and for safety perspective, alert on such problems like adverse events or DDI could concur with warning. (30).

We found that the use of more sophisticated, electronic comparison of clinically relevant potential DDIs identified by simple drug pairs reduced the incidence of DDI alerts by 70.8%. Additional clinical pharmacist review reduced the incidence of potentially serious DDIs by an additional 80.6%. Combination of the 2 methods reduced the incidence of apparent serious DDI by 94.3%. It is important that private and public health plan sponsors and PBM firms share available data on the types and incidence of clinically relevant potential medication errors and their methods used to make these determinations. Doing so will assist in better understanding the fundamentals of retrospective DUR (Drug Utilization review) intervention programs in ambulatory populations.

CONCLUSION

We found that organ transplant patients prescribed with more number of medications had an increase in the risk of drug related problems (DRPs), a total number of 224, like Drug interactions (n=214, 95.11%) adverse drug reactions (n=10, 4.44%). We found that due to the presence of co-morbidities there was an increase in the number of drugs used. We have also see the presence of a direct link between the number of drugs prescribed and Drug related problems. Recognition and resolution of these DRPs will cut down the numbers involved with the drug related morbidity and mortality in patients. The health professionals like clinical pharmacists should have enough knowledge regarding these problems and continuous efforts must be made to terminate or decrease DRPs. Clinical pharmacy services in organ transplant unit will help minimize the drug issues and also in management of same. Future research is to be done to analyse the extend of errors and prescribers response to such alerts. In addition to that many methods are to be adopted for most effective in accepting the response from prescribers to reduce the incidence of drug events in the hospital.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors of this article doesn't have any conflict of interest and can be for future recommendation.

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